

Biological and Pharmacological Activities of New Phenoxy- and Naphthoxyacetyl/propionyl Carbazole, Indole and Pyrrole Derivatives

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Manuscript received 14 January 1991, accepted 3 June 1992

Carbazole, indole and pyrrole derivatives possess various biological activities¹. Phenoxy- and 1- and 2-naphthoxyacetic and -propionic acids and their derivative also possess various biological activities². With an intention to prepare more active compounds, we have synthesised some new compounds belonging to carbazoles, indoles and pyrrole series by reacting appropriate substituted phenoxy and 1- and -2- naphthoxy derivatives with sodium salt of chloroacetic and propionic acid respectively in good yield (50–59%). Structures of the compounds (Table 1) have been established on the basis of spectral data and elemental analysis.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a Toshniwal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked on tlc. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. The compounds displayed principal ir bands at 2 905–2 930 (CH₃), 1 600–1 620 (C—O—N), 1 500–1 530 (C—H and C—C stretching and deformation vibration of selected heterocycles), 1 200–1 230 (C—O—C) and 1 030–1 035 cm⁻¹ (Ar—O).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	m. p. °C
1	H	Cl	H	H	H	H	96–98
2	H	H	H	Cl	H	H	260–62
3	H	Cl	H	Cl	H	H	120–21
4	H	Cl	H	H	Cl	H	244–46
5	H	Cl	H	Cl	H	Cl	258–60
6	H	H	H	H	H	H	218–20
7	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	H	221–22
8	H	H	H	H	H	H	214–16
9	H	H	H	H	H	H	98–100
10	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	H	94–96
11	H	H	H	H	H	H	108–10
12	H	H	H	H	H	H	302–04
13	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	H	110–12
14	H	H	H	H	H	H	120–22

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Phenoxy and naphthoxy acetic/propionic acids: Equimolecular quantities of phenoxy/1- and 2-naphthoxy and α -chloroacetic and α -chloropropionic acids (separately) were refluxed with 35% NaOH (3.5 ml) and water (15 ml) for 0.5 h and then the solution was evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was then dissolved in hot water (100 ml). The solution was cooled and treated with HCl to

(1-5)

(6, 7, 9, 10, 12, 13)

(8, 11, 14)

where HT = carbazole/indole/pyrrole

R = H, CH₃

yield the free acids. It was then extracted with ether and the ethereal solution on evaporation afforded the products.

Phenoxy- and naphthoxy acetyl/propionyl chlorides: To a solution of phenoxy/naphthoxy acetic and propionic acids (0.04 mol in 25 ml C₆H₆/EtOAc) was added SOCl₂ (0.04 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for about 6 h. The excess SOCl₂ was then distilled off under reduced pressure to get the desired products.

Phenoxy- and naphthoxy acetyl/propionyl carbazoles, indoles and pyrroles: To an ice-cooled solution of carbazole, indole and pyrrole (0.036–0.041 mol in 25 ml EtOH) was added 2N NaOH (5 ml). The dropwise addition of various acetyl and propionyl chlorides in the above solution with constant stirring afforded the final products.

Biological activities: Anti-inflammatory activity compounds (1–13) were tested³ in albino rats weighing (100–120 g fasted overnight). The animals were divided into three group of six rats each. A group of rats was treated orally with 100 mg of aqueous suspension of the compounds; another group was administered 100 mg/kg of aqueous suspension of ibuprofen and the control group was fed with the same volume of distilled water as the treated group. One hour after the administration,

the animals were injected with 0.05 ml of % carrageenan suspension in normal saline in the left hind paw planter aponeurosis. The measurement of foot volume were taken using Harries and Spencer mercury displacement technique with the help of plethysmometer immediately before and 1, 2 and 3 h after the carrageenan injection and the percent inhibition of inflammation after 3 h was calculated⁴ In comparison to ibuprofen (72.7% inhibition) compounds 4 (50.00%) and 5 (52.27%) displayed satisfactory activity.

The anthelmintic activities of compounds 9–11 were tested⁵ in earth worm (*Pheritima posthuma*). The solution of the compound was made in ethylene glycol (0.1%, w/v). The piperazine citrate (standard drug) was made of same concentration in ethylene glycol. Different sample solutions (2 ml) and standard solution (2 ml) were put normal saline solution⁶ (25 ml). Two living earth-worms (appropriate equal size, washed well with normal saline solution) were put in each of the above sample solutions. The time taken for complete paralysis and death of each worm was noted. The mean paralysis times and mean lethal respectively of the compounds along with standard and blank were recorded. The death of worm was confirmed by external stimuli. The experiment was carried out in duplicate. In comparison to piperazine citrate (mean paralysis time 61 min; mean lethal time 68 min), compound 10 showed greater activity (10 min; 46 min) among others.

The antibacterial activity of compounds 12–14 was evaluated by the Filter paper disc method⁷ against *Staphylococcus albus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Proteus spp.* Streptomycin (10 μg⁻¹) was used as standard. The compounds exhibited mild to moderate activity against the organisms.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to R.S.I.C., Lucknow, for the spectral data and microanalyses.

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